

Chlorhexidine in Endodontics Part III

Dr. Rajiv K. Chugh

National President, Indian Dental Association(2023-24)
 Visiting Professor, Sibar Institute of Dental Sciences, Guntur
 Member, Dental Council of India
 Vice Chairman, Pierre Fauchard Academy, India Section
 Secretary General, Indian Academy of Restorative Dentistry
 Editor-in-Chief (Asia), UPDENT- A Journal of Advanced Dentistry

Chlorhexidine as Intracanal Medicament

Calcium Hydroxide is one of the most versatile medications in dentistry, especially for use as an intracanal medicament in vital and non-vital teeth. It is believed to have many of the properties of an ideal root canal medicament, mainly due to its alkaline pH. It is bactericidal and neutralizes the remaining tissue debris in the root canal system. Calcium Hydroxide also promotes an alkalinizing osteogenic environment on the surrounding tissues through the continuous release of OH⁻ ions. Moreover, Calcium Hydroxide mediates the neutralization of lipopolysaccharides, helping in the cleansing the root canal. However, Calcium Hydroxide cannot be considered as a universal intracanal medicament, since it is not equally effective against all bacteria found in the root canal. Indeed, several studies have reported difficulty in eliminating enterococci effectively, as they tolerate high pH values, varying from 9 to 11.

Chlorhexidine has been used in endodontics and proposed as both an irrigant and an intracanal medicament. It is active against a wide range of microorganisms, such as Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (including *Enterococcus faecalis*), yeasts and fungi. One of the mechanisms that can explain its efficacy is based on the interaction between the positive charge of the molecule and the negatively charged phosphate groups on the bacterial cell wall, which allows the Chlorhexidine molecule to penetrate into the bacteria with toxic effects. Therefore, its antimicrobial activity is not related to its pH (between 5.5 to 7).

The antimicrobial activity of Chlorhexidine has also been tested for its use as an intracanal medicament alone or in combination with other substances.

When used as an intracanal medicament, Chlorhexidine is more effective than Calcium Hydroxide against *E. faecalis* infection in dentinal tubules. In fact, the antimicrobial activity of Chlorhexidine is reduced when combined with other substances, including Calcium Hydroxide, Calcium Hydroxide plus zinc oxide, among others. However, Chlorhexidine alone does not act as a physical barrier and does not present radiopacity. The use of Chlorhexidine gel as intracanal medicament is recommended for a short period of time (3-5 days), particularly in those cases where the canals were fully instrumented but could not be root-filled due to the lack of time. It is also recommended in cases of exudation (unpublished data), as it retains its antimicrobial activity in the presence of blood and other organic matters. Chlorhexidine gel is delivered into the canals with a syringe (e.g.: 24-gauge needle), being easily introduced and removed from the root canals.

On the other hand, the antimicrobial activity of Calcium Hydroxide increases with the combination with Chlorhexidine. Such combination aims to increase the antimicrobial properties of Calcium Hydroxide, while maintaining its biological characteristics, mechanical properties, action as a physical barrier. It has been reported that the antimicrobial effect of this association is not due to the Chlorhexidine molecule, but to the action of different byproducts generated by Chlorhexidine fragmentation. Such byproducts exhibit both antioxidant and pro-oxidant properties, and have a high pH. No traces of PCA have been found in the combination of Chlorhexidine with Calcium Hydroxide, due to the immediate degradation of Chlorhexidine, even though this mixture liberated reactive oxygen species (ROS) at all time points.

Studies have also shown that Calcium Hydroxide pastes added with Chlorhexidine gel, alone or with ZnO, have greater antimicrobial activity than those prepared with distilled water or saline.

The main advantages of this association are:

- a. Higher antimicrobial than that of Calcium Hydroxide alone;
- b. pH around 13, which is greater than that of Chlorhexidine alone (pH 5.5-7.0) and could help in the control of the inflammatory internal- and external- root resorption;
- c. Substantivity due to the presence of Chlorhexidine;
- d. Physical and chemical barrier better than that of 2% Chlorhexidine gel alone, preventing root canal re infection and interrupting the nutrient supply to the remaining bacteria;
- e. The contact angle of Calcium Hydroxide combined with Chlorhexidine is lower than that observed when Calcium Hydroxide is combined with water, increasing the wettability of the medicament, which may explain the increase in the antimicrobial activity of its association with Chlorhexidine;
- f. Chlorhexidine improves Calcium Hydroxide properties of reducing the endotoxin content in root canals *in vitro*;
- g. Diffusion through the dentinal tubules;
- h. Radiopacity.

The paste consistency should be similar to the toothpaste and its radiopacity is similar to that of the root dentin.

To act only as a physical barrier, this medicament can be used for a short period of time. It was observed that to achieve its best antimicrobial activity, it should stay for a period of 15 to 30 days inside the root canal, without being changed. The immediate antimicrobial action of the paste in the first 7 days seems

to be related to the antimicrobial effect of Chlorhexidine. This effect remains stable up to 14 days. The best action is observed within 30 days, with the diffusion of hydroxyl ions through the dentinal tubules (unpublished data). The use of a temporary sealing with composite ensures an effective seal, preventing contamination of the root canal and solubilization of the medicament by oral fluids, especially in periods longer than 7 days.

Diffusion into the Dentinal Tubules

It has been shown that 2% Chlorhexidine containing medicaments is able to diffuse into the dentin tubular structure and reach the outer root surface, exerting antimicrobial action. Therefore, the root canal could be considered as a reservoir for the release of intracanal medicament to the whole dentin and to the external root surface Sodium Hypochlorite.

Disinfection of Obturation Cones (Gutta-Percha and Resilon Cones)

The efficacy of Sodium Hypochlorite and Chlorhexidine as auxiliary chemical substances and their action as disinfectant agents of gutta-percha cones do not involve additional costs to clinicians, since these substances are commonly used in endodontic therapy. Chlorhexidine has the ability to kill vegetative forms within short periods of time. However, this agent is not able to eliminate some spores, as does Sodium Hypochlorite.

As a strong oxidizing agent, 5.25% Sodium Hypochlorite is able to cause local changes in surface roughness of gutta-percha cones. Moreover, formation of crystals on the surface of gutta-percha cones has been identified after a rapid sterilization with 2.5% and 5.25% Sodium Hypochlorite showing that the final rinse with distilled water is essential, especially when Sodium Hypochlorite is used for cone disinfection. Other studies showed that 2% Chlorhexidine did not change gutta-percha cone properties after exposure for up to 30 min, suggesting that this substance is less harmful to the structure of gutta-percha. It was also found that 5.25% Sodium Hypochlorite and 2% Chlorhexidine did not produce any changes on Resilon surface. Resilon cones exposed to Chlorhexidine gel presented some residual antibacterial action. The clinical importance of Chlorhexidine release in endodontic cones might be related to its immediate antimicrobial effect inside the root canal, during the obturation time.

Chlorhexidine and Sodium Hypochlorite lead to an increase in the surface free energy (wettability) of the gutta-percha cones and Resilon surfaces, thereby interfering positively with the adhesion mechanism. This change can be due to chemical modifications on the surface of these materials caused by the action of these solutions. Comparing the two solutions, Chlorhexidine was a better disinfectant compared with Sodium Hypochlorite that is, presented high values of surface free energy. Cones disinfected with Chlorhexidine presented smaller contact angles than Sodium Hypochlorite, favouring the interaction between the solid surface (cone) and the liquid, in this case, the sealer.

Other Uses in the Endodontic Therapy

Before 1990's, Chlorhexidine gluconate was used in Endodontics as an irrigating solution, but always in a liquid form. One of the first reports of its use in Endodontics dates back to 1964, demonstrating its effectiveness in enhancing radicular dentin permeability. Chlorhexidine in a gel presentation was evaluated by Siqueira and de Uzeda as an intracanal medicament, demonstrating good performance. In 2001, Ferraz et al. proposed the use of Chlorhexidine gel as endodontic irrigant.

Chlorhexidine can be used during all phases of the root canal treatment, including in the disinfection of the operatory field, due to its antimicrobial and substantivity properties. Chlorhexidine

has been recommended as an alternative to Sodium Hypochlorite, especially in cases of open apex, root resorption, foramen enlargement and root perforation, due to its biocompatibility, or in cases of allergy related to bleaching solutions.

Clinical investigations have been performed using 2% Chlorhexidine gel for root canal preparation in the full extension of the root canal, with foraminal patency and enlargement, followed by root canal filling in the same visit. The results showed that approximately 93% of the patients did report postoperative pain (unpublished data). With foramen enlargement, the risk of irrigant extrusion through the apex increases, favouring the use of Chlorhexidine, for being less irritating to the periapical tissues than Sodium Hypochlorite and not inducing pain. Irrigation with 17% EDTA for a better smear layer removal is recommended after instrumentation of the root canals with Chlorhexidine, which should be previously removed with distilled water.

Chlorhexidine gel can also be used for modelling gutta-percha cones, which improves their adaptation to the apical dentin wall (unpublished data).

The use of Chlorhexidine gel during retreatment has also been investigated. *In vitro*, groups that used Chlorhexidine gel with manual or rotary instrumentation showed smaller debris extrusion as well as the cleanest root canal walls than the ones where solvents were used (unpublished data). A clinical investigation of retreatment cases has reported that chemo-mechanical preparation with 2% Chlorhexidine gel was more effective in reducing bacteria (99.61%) than endotoxin (60.6%).

Adverse Effects

No adverse effects have been published regarding Chlorhexidine use as irrigant or intracanal medicament. However, the direct effect in an *in vitro* test on human stem cells of apical papilla showed lack of viable cells after its use. The *in vitro* cytotoxic effect of the Chlorhexidine on human osteoblastic cells seems to be dose dependent. There is a consensus that all irrigating substances when applied direct to cells would impact to a certain degree on cell viability. On the other hand, animal studies have shown that 2.0% Chlorhexidine did not induce intense inflammatory response when injected into the peritoneal cavity of mice or in root canals of dogs, when used as intracanal medicament.

Chlorhexidine adverse effects are usually more related to its topical or oral application. The use of Chlorhexidine dental gel dentifrices and mouthwashes has been associated with reversible discoloration of the tongue, teeth, and silicate or composite restorations. Removal of the brownish discoloration can be done with abrasive pastes or instruments. However, it should not be used concomitantly with dentifrices, as Chlorhexidine interacts with detergents and fluoride in toothpaste. The Chlorhexidine products should be used 30 min after brushing.

Transient taste disturbances and a burning sensation of the tongue may occur on initial use. Oral desquamation and occasional parotid gland swelling have been reported with the use of mouthwash. The incidence of skin irritation and hypersensitivity is low when Chlorhexidine is applied at its recommended concentrations. Strong solutions may cause irritation of the conjunctive and other sensitive tissues, such as brain, meninges and middle ear. Syringes and needles that have been immersed in Chlorhexidine solutions should be thoroughly rinsed with sterile water or saline before use.

(It's a review of literature and not an original article)